

Directional Residual Stabilization for High–Peclet-Number Advection–Diffusion Problems

GPU-Accelerated Implementation in the Vanadis System

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Abstract

High–Peclet-number advection–diffusion problems remain challenging for classical finite element formulations due to numerical instabilities and excessive artificial diffusion. This preprint introduces the conceptual foundations of a directional residual stabilization approach designed to enhance robustness and directional accuracy in strongly advection-dominated regimes. The method is implemented in *Vanadis*, a GPU-accelerated environmental simulation system for large-scale three-dimensional transport modelling. For a grid of 2.8 million nodes, the solution of the linear system arising from a single advection–diffusion time step completes in approximately 6 seconds on an NVIDIA GTX 1060 GPU, demonstrating the practical efficiency of the approach even on consumer-grade hardware. The focus of this document is on the motivation, conceptual structure, and computational context of the method, while detailed mathematical formulations, algorithmic components, and numerical benchmarks will be presented in a forthcoming journal publication.

1 Introduction

High–Peclet-number advection–diffusion problems remain a persistent challenge for classical finite element formulations. Standard Galerkin methods often produce spurious oscillations, while traditional stabilisation techniques—such as SUPG [1], GLS [2], CIP [3] or Scharfetter–Gummel [4]—may introduce excessive artificial diffusion or require problem-specific tuning. These limitations become particularly restrictive in large-scale environmental simulations, where directional accuracy and numerical robustness are essential.

This preprint introduces the conceptual foundations of Directional Residual Stabilisation (DR), a novel stabilisation philosophy designed to enhance robustness in strongly advective regimes. DR employs a directional treatment of residual information to selectively suppress numerically unstable components while preserving physically meaningful gradients. The detailed mathematical formulation is part of an ongoing patent procedure (application no. P.455475) and will be presented in a forthcoming journal publication. Here, we focus on the motivation, conceptual structure, and computational context of the method.

The DR concept is implemented in *Vanadis*, a GPU-accelerated three-dimensional air-pollution transport model designed for real-time environmental simulations. *Vanadis* employs an element-by-element finite element architecture, a BDF2–Gear time-integration scheme, and a diagonally preconditioned DBCG solver, enabling efficient large-scale computations on modern GPU hardware.

2 Background and Motivation

Environmental transport modelling imposes stringent numerical requirements:

- Stability in high-Peclet regimes — the numerical method must remain robust under strongly advective conditions,
- Directional accuracy — transported scalars must preserve physically meaningful anisotropic features,
- Scalability to multi-million-node meshes — simulations must remain efficient as spatial resolution increases,
- Compatibility with massively parallel architectures — algorithms must exploit modern GPU and multi-core hardware effectively.

These requirements are particularly demanding in large-scale environmental applications, where numerical stability, physical fidelity, and computational performance must be achieved simultaneously.

3 GPU-Accelerated Implementation in Vanadis

Vanadis is a dynamic 3D air-pollution transport model designed for real-time environmental applications. Its computational pipeline emphasises:

- fully GPU-resident execution,
- high arithmetic intensity,
- minimal memory traffic,
- element-wise parallelism,
- scalability to non-uniform structured 3D grids.

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The DR stabilisation integrates seamlessly into this architecture due to its strictly local structure and independence from global matrix assembly.

Vanadis employs an element-by-element finite element formulation optimised for CUDA [5], a BDF2–Gear time-integration scheme [6], and a diagonally preconditioned DBCG solver [7].

The DR formulation preserves the total transported mass throughout the simulation. Because stabilisation is applied only in the flow direction, no artificial cross-stream diffusion is introduced, and plume evolution remains physically consistent. Mass preservation is maintained across both CPU and GPU implementations.

The solver employs an element-by-element (EBE) strategy that avoids global matrix assembly, reduces memory usage, and improves data locality. GPU acceleration is achieved through CUDA kernels operating on element-level data, with CPU and GPU pathways sharing identical numerical logic. The resulting system matrix is diagonally dominant, making it well suited for GPU-based DBCG. A lightweight diagonal preconditioner is used to maintain robustness while keeping GPU kernels simple and efficient.

Comparison with the Pasquill dispersion model [8] shows consistent plume behaviour and concentration ranges, confirming the physical correctness of the DR-stabilised formulation. The solver remains stable in strongly advection-dominated regimes.

Benchmark tests indicate that a full advection–diffusion update for a grid of 2.8 million nodes completes in approximately 6 seconds per time step on an NVIDIA GTX 1060 GPU, placing the method firmly within the real-time regime for environmental simulations. On an Intel i5-4590 CPU paired with a GTX 1060 3 GB GPU, a 20-step simulation (0–2000 s, $\Delta t = 100$ s) completed in approximately 10 minutes and remained numerically stable throughout, exhibiting no temporal or spatial oscillations.

5 Applications

The DR method and the *Vanadis* system are intended for large-scale environmental modelling, including:

- atmospheric pollutant dispersion,
- scalar transport in the atmospheric boundary layer,
- emergency response simulations,
- real-time decision support systems.

These application areas benefit directly from the method’s stability, directional accuracy, and GPU-accelerated performance, making DR and Vanadis suitable for both research-grade and operational workflows.

6 Conclusions

This preprint presents a concise overview of the conceptual foundations of Directional Residual Stabilisation (DR) and its integration into a GPU-accelerated environmental simulation system. The combination of DR stabilisation, BDF2–Gear time integration, and GPU-accelerated element-wise computation provides a robust and efficient pathway for next-generation air-quality modelling.

A detailed mathematical formulation, numerical benchmarks, and a comprehensive performance evaluation will be presented in a forthcoming journal publication.

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